

VALIDATION QUESTIONNAIRE

1 resposta

[Publicar análise](#)

Part 1 - Knowledge Correctness

1. The identified concepts are semantically correct.

 Copiar

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

2. The definitions assigned to the concepts are appropriate for the domain.

 Copiar

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

3. The relationships established between concepts are correct.

 Copiar

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

4. I did not identify relevant conceptual inconsistencies.

 Copiar

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

5. The represented knowledge is technically aligned with real-world domain practice.

 Copiar

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

6. The terminology used is appropriate.

 Copiar

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

7. Please identify any incorrect or inadequately represented concepts.

1 resposta

None

8. Please indicate any relationships that should be corrected or removed.

1 resposta

None

Part 2 - Knowledge Completeness

1. The main domain concepts covered to a level that can be considered satisfactory.

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

2. The essential relationships between concepts are represented.

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

3. I did not identify relevant knowledge gaps.

 Copiar

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

4. The representation allows a clear understanding of the domain's overall structure.

 Copiar

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

5. Which important concepts were not included?

1 resposta

None

6. Which relationships should be considered?

1 resposta

All important concepts from the input data were included. Future steps should focus on including more relationships and more information about the domain.

7. Which aspects are superficial and should be further detailed?

1 resposta

See answer to question #6. The superficiality of the aspects is due to small input data.

Part 3 - Application Effort

1. The approach reduced the time required to structure domain knowledge.

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

2. The approach reduced overall cognitive effort.

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

3. The identification of concepts was facilitated.

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

4. The identification of relationships was facilitated.

 Copiar

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

5. The validation of knowledge was facilitated.

 Copiar

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

6. Compared to a traditional approach, the application was less demanding.

 Copiar

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

7. The tools were easy to use.

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

8. The application required substantial manual effort.

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

9. Which steps required the greatest effort?

1 resposta

Understanding the complexity of the knowledge graph which was a new tool for me to interact with knowledge. Once understood it was easy to use.

10. What could be improved to further reduce effort?

1 resposta

Guide users on how to use the knowledge graph.

Part 4 - Acceptance of the Approach

1. The approach improves the quality of the process of acquired knowledge.

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

2. The approach contributes to better knowledge organization.

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

3. The approach facilitates knowledge acquired validation.

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

4. I would use this approach in real-world activities.

 Copiar

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

5. I would recommend this approach to other professionals.

 Copiar

1 resposta

- Strongly disagree
- Partially disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Partially agree
- Strongly agree

Part 6 - Overall Evaluation

Overall, I evaluate the approach as:

 Copiar

1 resposta

Final comments about the approach:

1 resposta

Different but helpful way to structure information. Thank you!

Este conteúdo não foi criado nem aprovado pelo Google. - [Entre em contato com o proprietário do formulário](#) - [Termos de Serviço](#) - [Política de Privacidade](#)

Este formulário parece suspeito? [Denunciar](#)

Google Formulários

